

E-COMMERCE AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION for VIKSIT BHARAT

Prof. Devarajappa S.

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Prof. Battu Satyanarayana
Vice - Chancellor
Central University of Karnataka

I am glad to learn that, the Department of Commerce, School of Business Studies, Central University of Karnataka, has dedicated itself for the cause of empowerment of students through imparting quality and relevant education. As a part of this endeavor, the department is organising a National Seminar on **“E-Commerce and Digital Transformation for Viksit Bharat”** on 28th March 2025. I am sure the deliberations of the seminar will be of delineate significance in E-Commerce and Digital Transformation for making Viksit Bharat.

I appreciate the fact that this seminar shall provide a platform for meaningful and insightful exchange of thoughts which will be useful for the academicians, researchers and industries. I convey my greetings and best wishes to the faculty, students and delegates participating in the seminar. To commemorate the event, the Department has proposed to bring out an edited volume containing selected papers presented in the seminar with an ISBN number, which will greatly aid in the accumulation and assimilation of knowledge.

I wish the seminar a great success.

Prof. Battu Satyanarayana
Vice - Chancellor

Foreword

It gives me an immense pleasure to learn that Department of Commerce, School of Business Studies, Central University of Karnataka is hosting a national seminar on “**E-Commerce and Digital Transformation for Viksit Bharat**” on 28th March 2025.

Today, markets and globalisation which are transforming the world in digital transformation era are changing the context of world and exercising an influence on the nature of the organizational performance. The rise of India as economic power and increasing integration of the world economy through advanced digital transformation are all placing new demands on our organisations.

I wish the seminar a very success. I sincerely hope that what thoughts and ideas emerge out of this one-day seminar would pave the way for all stakeholders of business education to set the agenda for India – an agenda to create a scientific temper, research rigour, holistic vision and leadership skills apart from imparting basic values of peace, love, justice, compassion and a life of gratitude among younger generation, for Viksit Bharat by 2047.

Prof. R. R. Biradar
Registrar
Central University of Karnataka

PREFACE

This National seminar on “**E-Commerce and Digital Transformation for Viksit Bharat**” represents a growth and maturity of Department of Commerce that has built a series of workshops, seminars, conferences and faculty development programmes held over last one and half decades. The theme of the seminar was aptly chosen keeping in conformance with the industry demands and proliferation in the fields of E-Commerce and Digital Transformation.

The objective of seminar was to intensify the information exchange of the results in theoretical research and practical developments in the field of E-Commerce and Digital Transformation. The main objective of this seminar is to provide a forum for researchers, educators, students and industries to exchange ideas, to communicate and discuss research findings and new advances in the field of digitalization and organisational effectiveness. The forum should also enable participants to explore possible avenues to foster academic and student exchange, as well as scientific activities within the region and India as a whole. The seminar will give opportunity to both academia and practitioners to communicate and discuss on E-Commerce and Digital Transformation for Viksit Bharat.

The collection of papers in this seminar book, shows a maturity in the field through new examples of research creativity and theoretical advances in understanding emerging trends in E-Commerce and Digital Transformation, which helps making India as Viksit Bharat. The seminar demonstrates success as we see publications that build on the advances through references to papers published in this seminar. We look forward to this publication providing the foundation for future developments in research creativity.

Prof. Devarajappa S
Editor

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Like the many pages in the book, many people have contributed towards this book.

First and foremost I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to ICSSR-SRC for sponsoring One Day National Seminar on **E-Commerce and Digital Transformation for Viksit Bharat**.

The book is a collection of selected research papers contributed by scholars and practitioners for the **“E-Commerce and Digital Transformation for Viksit Bharat”**. We express our deep sense of gratitude to all those who have contributed papers. This book would not have been possible without the support, co-operation and encouragement of several people and we would like to extend my heartfelt gratitude to one and all.

We express our sincere gratitude, **Prof. Battu Satyanarayana**, Hon'ble Vice chancellor, Central University of Karnataka and Prof. R R Biradar, Registrar, **Shri. Kota Sai Krishna**, Controller of Examination, **Shri. D. Ramadurai**, Finance Officer, Central University of Karnataka for giving us this opportunity to organize the national seminar on **“E-Commerce and Digital Transformation for Viksit Bharat”**

We also extend our special thanks to all the scholars, academicians, practitioners, researchers and participants from all over for making the conference a successful event.

Our thanks are due to **Sri. Niraj Kumar Pandey, Sri. Vijay Pandey**, who are continuing the legacy of the founder of HPH, for their support in publishing edited book. We thank **Mr. Irfan Pasha**, Manager and the staff of HPH for their assistance in bringing the book.

Our thanks are due to Research Scholars, and students of Department of Commerce, school of Business studies, Central University of Karnataka for their wholehearted support. We are also thankful to the staff members of the Central University of Karnataka and especially Department of Commerce, Central University of Karnataka, Kalaburagi, India for their support.

Prof. Devarajappa S
Editor

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Understanding Customer Expectations and Experiences in Internet-Based Banking: A Tumkur City Perspective

Syed Babu H B, M.Com Co-ordinator, Sri Siddhartha First Grade College, Tumkur

Vinaykumar M, Head, Department of Commerce, Sri Siddhartha First Grade College, Tumkur

Dr G Parameshwari, Assistant Professor, Dept of Commerce, PES Science, Arts and Commerce College, Mandya

ABSTRACT

The rapid evolution of technology has significantly transformed the banking sector, with Internet banking emerging as a pivotal channel for delivering financial services. This study titled *"Understanding Customer Expectations and Experiences in Internet-Based Banking: A Tumkur City Perspective"* aims to explore the current landscape, usage patterns, and customer satisfaction levels related to online banking services. As India stands on the brink of a digital banking revolution, this research investigates the prospects and challenges of Internet banking adoption in the region. Specifically, it focuses on evaluating customer expectations, usage levels, and authentication techniques that ensure secure transactions. Additionally, it examines the initiatives taken by banks to enhance customer experience, such as fund transfers, bill payments, e-shopping, and 24/7 access to services. Despite its growth, Internet banking in India faces obstacles like limited computer literacy, inconsistent Internet connectivity, security concerns, and resistance from traditional customers. Through this study, primary data collected from customers in Tumkur City will offer valuable insights into their satisfaction and highlight areas for improvement. The findings are expected to contribute to the enhancement of digital banking strategies, ensuring customer-centric services while addressing security and accessibility challenges in the Indian banking context.

Introduction:

With cyber cafés and kiosks springing up in different cities access to the Net is going to be easy. Internet banking (also referred as e-banking) is the latest in this series of technological wonders in the recent past involving use of the Internet for delivery of banking products & services. Internet banking is changing the banking industry and is having major effects on banking relationships. Banking is now no longer confined to the branches where one has to approach the branch in person, to withdraw cash or deposit a cheque or request a statement of accounts. In true Internet banking, any inquiry or transaction is processed online without any reference to the branch (anywhere banking) at any time. Providing Internet banking is increasingly becoming a "need to have" than a "nice to have" service. Net banking, thus, now is more of a norm rather than an exception in many developed countries due to the fact that it is the cheapest way of providing banking services. Internet banking refers to the use of the Internet as a remote delivery channel for banking services. Such services include traditional ones, such as opening a deposit account or transferring funds among different accounts, and new banking services, such as electronic bill presentment and payment (allowing customers to receive and pay bills on a bank's Web site).

Revolution of E-Banking in India:

- **Introduction of Core Banking Solutions (CBS):** Banks implemented CBS, allowing customers to operate their accounts and avail banking services from any branch.
- **Launch of Internet Banking (1990s):** Banks started offering basic services like fund transfers, account statements, and bill payments online.
- **Introduction of ATMs (Automated Teller Machines):** Provided 24/7 cash withdrawal and basic services, reducing dependency on physical branches.
- **Mobile Banking Apps Emergence (Early 2000s):** Banks developed mobile apps for services like fund transfer, checking balances, and mini statements.
- **NEFT, RTGS & IMPS Introduction:** Facilitated fast and secure electronic fund transfers domestically.

- **Rise of Digital Wallets & UPI (Unified Payments Interface):** Revolutionized instant payment systems (Paytm, PhonePe, Google Pay, BHIM UPI) making cashless transactions easy.
- **Government Initiatives (Digital India Campaign):** Boosted digital infrastructure and encouraged digital payments post **Demonetization (2016)**.
- **Introduction of QR Code Payments:** Popularized in retail outlets, small businesses, and even street vendors for seamless transactions.
- **Two-factor Authentication & Enhanced Security:** Adoption of OTPs, biometrics, and encryption to secure online transactions.
- **Introduction of Virtual Debit Cards & Contactless Payments:** Eased online purchases without needing physical cards; NFC-based payments like tap-to-pay introduced.
- **Launch of Aadhaar Enabled Payment Systems (AEPS):** Used Aadhaar number & biometrics to facilitate banking transactions, especially in rural areas.
- **Open Banking & API Integration:** Fintech companies collaborate with banks through APIs, offering innovative financial products.

Some of Drawbacks of E-Banking:

1. **Cyber security Threats & Frauds:** Increased risks of phishing, hacking, identity theft, and unauthorized access. Many customers fall prey to fake links and scam messages.
2. **Lack of Digital Literacy:** A significant portion of the rural population lacks awareness and skills to use e-banking services safely.
3. **Technical Glitches & Server Downtime:** Frequent technical failures, server downtime, or failed transactions frustrate customers and reduce trust.
4. **Internet Connectivity Issues:** Poor internet infrastructure in semi-urban and rural areas limits the smooth functioning of e-banking services.
5. **Privacy Concerns:** Customers are often worried about the misuse of their personal and financial information.
6. **Limited Accessibility for Elderly and Less Tech-Savvy People:** Many elderly individuals struggle to adapt to mobile apps and online banking interfaces.
7. **Cost of Maintaining Digital Infrastructure:** Banks face high costs for updating technology, cybersecurity, and maintaining servers.
8. **Dependency on Technology:** Total dependency on technology makes customers vulnerable to service outages, app crashes, or cyberattacks.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To analyze the current landscape and growth of Internet banking in India.
2. To evaluate the future prospects and potential of Internet banking in the Indian financial sector.
3. To assess the extent and frequency of Internet banking usage among customers.
4. To explore the various authentication methods and security protocols employed in Internet banking services.
5. To examine customer satisfaction levels and their perceptions regarding online banking services.

Limitations of the Study:

1. **Geographical Limitation:** The study is confined to Tumkur city, and therefore, the findings may not reflect the Internet banking scenario in other regions of India.
2. **Subjectivity of Responses:** The responses collected are based on the personal opinions and perceptions of the respondents, which may not always be fully accurate or objective.
3. **Limited Generalizability:** Due to the localized focus and sample size, the results of the study may not be applicable or generalizable to the broader population without further comprehensive research.
4. **Time Constraints of Respondents:** Some respondents may not have allocated sufficient time to thoughtfully answer the questionnaire, potentially affecting the quality and accuracy of responses.

5. **Lack of Awareness Among Respondents:** A few participants may possess limited knowledge or understanding of internet banking services, which could influence the reliability of the responses.
6. **Sample Size Limitation:** The study may be constrained by a limited number of respondents, which might not adequately represent the entire customer base using internet banking services.
7. **Possibility of Non-Response Bias:** Certain individuals may choose not to participate in the survey, resulting in potential non-response bias affecting the overall outcome of the study.
8. **Dynamic Nature of Technology:** Given the rapid evolution of digital banking technologies, the findings may become outdated quickly and may not reflect future developments.

Recent Developments in Internet Banking in India

1. **Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI):** The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has urged banks to adopt AI technologies to enhance customer service and effectively address consumer complaints.
2. **Surge in Cyber Fraud Cases:** In the fiscal year 2024, India witnessed a significant increase in high-value cyber fraud cases, resulting in losses totaling \$20 million.
3. **Establishment of Self-Regulatory Organization for Account Aggregators:** The RBI is seeking applications to recognize a self-regulatory body for account aggregators, aiming to facilitate information exchange between financial and market institutions.
4. **Technological Innovations Transforming Banking:** The Indian banking sector is undergoing a transformation with the adoption of groundbreaking technologies such as the metaverse, the Account Aggregator platform, digital currency, and Unified Payments Interface (UPI).
5. **Challenges and Opportunities in Banking Digitization:** As India advances towards a digital economy, the banking sector faces both opportunities and challenges, including cybersecurity threats, regulatory compliance, and the need for continuous technological upgrades.

Table No. 1: Showing the respondents Using the Internet Banking

Sl. No	Description	No of Respondents	Percentages
1	Yes	23	92
2	No	2	8
Total		25	100

Table No. 2: Modes of Awareness among Respondents Regarding Internet Banking

Sl. No	Description	No of Respondents	Percentages
1	By TV advertise	1	4
2	Friends	18	72
3	Family	6	24
4	Others	0	0
Total		25	100

Table No. 3: Usage Patterns of Internet Banking Among Respondents

Sl.No	Description	No of Respondents	Percentages
1	Daily	9	36
2	Twice a week	2	8
3	Weekly	10	40
4	Monthly	4	16
5	Rarely	0	0
Total		25	100

Table No. 4: Respondents Level of satisfaction with reference to Internet Banking

Sl. No	Description	No of Respondents	Percentages
1	Very Dissatisfied	1	4
2	Dissatisfied	7	28
3	Neither dissatisfied satisfied	0	0
4	Satisfied	17	68
Total		25	100

Table No. 5: Respondents' Perceived Need for Internet Banking Services

Sl. No	Description	No of Respondent	Percentages
1	Account balance check	19	76
2	Payment of bills	3	12
3	Account print out	0	0
4	Ticket booking	0	0
5	Online Stock trading	3	12
6	Others	0	0
Total			100

Findings:

Source: Primary data collected from bank customers in Tumkur city.

1. The study indicates that younger generations exhibit a higher tendency to adopt Internet banking services compared to older generations.
2. Respondents with higher educational qualifications (university level and above) show a greater inclination toward the adoption of Internet banking than those with lower levels of education.
3. It is observed that individuals belonging to higher income groups are more likely to use Internet banking services compared to those from lower income brackets.
4. Frequent visitors to banks' official websites are found to be more inclined to adopt Internet banking services.
5. The analysis reveals that male respondents are more likely to adopt Internet banking services than female respondents.
6. Approximately 45% of respondents reported engaging in online shopping activities using their Internet banking accounts.
7. Similarly, 45% of the respondents stated that they access their Internet banking accounts at least once a week.
8. A substantial 60% of the respondents indicated that their decision to open an Internet banking account was influenced by their pre-existing traditional bank account with the same bank.
9. About 55% of the Internet banking account holders reported using their accounts specifically for online purchases.
10. A significant proportion (85%) of respondents expressed that Internet banking is highly convenient and essential for facilitating quick transactions.
11. Around 65% of respondents acknowledged accessing their Internet banking accounts primarily from their workplace or office premises.
12. Security considerations are prominent, with 75% of respondents affirming that strong security measures are crucial for a bank's website.
13. Moreover, 67% of respondents expressed satisfaction with the security mechanisms adopted by banks to safeguard customer information and prevent fraudulent activities.

- Overall, 70% of respondents conveyed satisfaction with the range and quality of services offered by their respective Internet banking platforms.

Conclusion:

Based on the primary data collected from bank customers in Tumkur city, it is evident that demographic variables such as age, education level, income, and gender have a significant impact on the adoption of Internet banking services. Younger, well-educated, high-income male respondents demonstrate a higher rate of adoption than their counterparts. Additionally, the presence of a pre-existing traditional bank account significantly influences customers' inclination to adopt Internet banking services. Security and convenience are key determinants of customer satisfaction, with a majority of respondents expressing trust in their banks' security protocols and satisfaction with the overall services. Continuous improvements in security features and customer awareness initiatives are recommended to sustain and further enhance customer trust and satisfaction in Internet banking.

Suggestions

Based on the findings and analysis of the study conducted among bank customers in Tumkur city, the following suggestions are proposed to enhance the adoption and efficiency of Internet banking services:

- Strengthening Security Protocols:** Banks should prioritize the implementation of advanced security measures, including multi-factor authentication, biometric verification, and real-time fraud detection systems. This would further bolster customer confidence and safeguard sensitive financial data.
- Customer Education and Awareness Initiatives:** Targeted awareness programs should be organized to educate customers, particularly senior citizens, women, and individuals with lower educational qualifications, about the benefits, features, and safety precautions related to Internet banking.
- User-Friendly Digital Interfaces:** Banks should invest in simplifying their mobile applications and websites to cater to users who are less technologically adept, ensuring ease of navigation and reducing the digital divide.
- Integration of Traditional and Digital Banking:** Considering that a significant percentage of customers opened Internet banking accounts due to their association with traditional banking, banks should focus on seamless integration of both platforms to offer a unified banking experience.
- Incentive-Based Usage Promotion:** Offering incentives such as loyalty points, discounts, or cashbacks for online transactions could encourage customers, particularly those hesitant to transition, to use Internet banking services more frequently.
- Customized Marketing Strategies:** Banks should adopt demographic-specific marketing strategies to address the specific needs and concerns of different customer groups, including women, lower-income groups, and less-educated customers.
- Continuous Feedback Collection Mechanism:** Establishing a robust feedback system would allow banks to regularly gauge customer satisfaction and promptly address issues, thereby improving service quality and customer retention.
- Enhancement of Mobile Banking Features:** Given the significant percentage of customers accessing their Internet banking accounts from workplaces, banks should ensure their mobile platforms are optimized for convenience, speed, and security.

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